

Finding Women in History Assessments in Secondary Schools: An interim report on 2023 History GCSE and A-Level assessment papers in England

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Summary

This report examines the representation of women across all time periods, topics and options offered in History GCSE, AS and A-Level exam papers issued in June 2023 by the three largest exam boards in England: AQA, Edexcel and OCR. It reveals that women are critically underrepresented in comparison to men in GCSE/Key Stage 4 (KS4) and A-Level/Key Stage 5 (KS5) assessments. In 991 questions across 219 exam papers, students were directed to discuss women in their answers for 6% of questions, whereas they were directed to discuss men in 36.5% of questions. Out of 357 instances of individuals being named in questions, only 31 instances were women, and 326 were men. 9 of these female instances were the same person – Elizabeth I – who was the most frequently named woman across all exam documentation. The named women who featured most regularly in the exam papers were typically royal women, modern political leaders, or suffragettes. Most questions on women were focused on the suffrage movements of the twentieth century, demonstrating a significant lack of named women in pre-modern topics. The representation of non-elite women and women from outside the UK and Europe was minimal. This report follows initial findings published in November 2024 on behalf of the [Teaching Medieval Women](#) group, which focused on women in the medieval exam content for years 2022–2023.¹ The present report, covering exam content from all time periods issued in 2023, found that women are underrepresented at all exam levels by all the exam boards, and confirmed that medieval topics require the most urgent revision. Our current report calls for a systematic reform of assessments at KS4 and KS5 to ensure that equal, representative and inclusive History is being taught in schools. It provides a series of recommendations to improve the visibility of women across all exam content offered to History GCSE, AS and A Level students.

¹ Natasha Hodgson and Catherine Gower, 'Finding Medieval Women in School Assessments: An interim report on GCSE and A-Level assessment papers in England 2022-2023', Zenodo (2024), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14193270>, accessed 14 July 2025.

Introduction

In November 2024, Teaching Medieval Women produced an interim report, *Finding Medieval Women in School Assessments*, based on a survey of 86 GCSE and A Level exam papers with medieval content issued by the three main exam boards, AQA, Edexcel, and OCR, across the 2022 and 2023 series. This report found that women were critically underrepresented in these exam papers with students directed to discuss women in their answers for only 2% of questions compared to 40% of questions on men.² Details from this report were submitted to the [Department for Education's Curriculum and Assessment Review](#) in November 2024.³ Despite stating a commitment to inclusivity in the review's interim report issued in March 2025 and the wish to ensure that every student could 'see themselves represented in the curriculum', the review so far has done little to address specific issues relating to women and gender.⁴

In our new report, the survey of materials was extended to cover all of the 219 exam papers issued by AQA, OCR and Edexcel for the 2023 series to see if this pattern extended to non-medieval papers. We have found that while medieval papers are the most likely to exclude women in quantifiable terms, women are underrepresented across all periods, exam levels and exam boards.

Key findings summarised

In the June 2023 exam papers and mark schemes for AQA, Edexcel and OCR:

- Women are disproportionately underrepresented in comparison to men in assessments across all exam levels, exam boards and topic periods.
- There are no women at all in 76 out of the total 219 papers assessed – they are not mentioned in essay questions, in source extracts or in the mark scheme. Only one of the 219 papers features no men, based on the same criteria.

² Natasha Hodgson and Catherine Gower, 'Finding Medieval Women in School Assessments: An Interim Report on GCSE and A-level Assessment Papers in England 2022-2023', *Zenodo* (2024), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14193270>, accessed 14 July 2025.

³ For more on this review, see DfE, 'Curriculum and assessment review', <https://www.gov.uk/government/groups/curriculum-and-assessment-review>, accessed 14 July 2025.

⁴ DfE, 'Curriculum and Assessment Review Interim Report' (March 2025), p. 28, https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/6821d69eced319d02c9060e3/Curriculum_and_Assessment_Review_interim_report.pdf, accessed 14 July 2025.

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- Students were directed to discuss women (either as named individuals or in groups⁵) in 6% of all exam essay questions. Based on the same criteria, they were directed to discuss men in 36.5% of questions.
- For every 1 named woman identified in an exam question there were 10.5 named men.
- Named women appeared more frequently in questions for A Level exam content (19 named women) than GCSE (5 women) or AS Level papers (7 women).
- Out of 163 historians quoted in the exam papers, only 22 were women.
- Women were better represented in exam content for early modern topics than medieval and modern topics, but this may be due to the overrepresentation of 'exceptional' figures like Elizabeth I.
- Medieval papers largely excluded women. In 2023 students were directed to discuss women in their answer for 2 questions in medieval papers while 68 questions focused on men.
- Out of the top 11 most referenced women in the 2023 series, 9 were royal women. 6 of the 11 were queens regnant or queens consort of England. The most frequently named woman across all exam papers was Elizabeth I.⁶

Sources and methods

The source material for this study comprised the question papers and mark schemes issued for the summer 2023 series by the 3 largest exam boards for History in England: AQA, Edexcel and OCR. 219 exam papers were consulted, of which 59 were GCSE papers, 47 were AS, and 113 were A Level. OCR offered the biggest range of papers (91), followed by AQA (69), then Edexcel (59). As OCR offered two separate History GCSEs (GCSE 'A' (Explaining the Modern World) and GCSE 'B' (Schools History Project), these were assessed as separate units.

⁵ To maximise the number of instances we could quantify, groups here were defined by roles which might be interpreted as gender-specific as well as the words 'men' or 'women', so, for example, 'suffragettes' or 'priests'.

⁶ Three women (Elizabeth Woodville, Emmeline Pankhurst, and Mary II) share ninth place in the list of most referenced women (see Appendix C) so we refer to the 'top 11' most-referenced women rather than the 'top 10'.

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In order to identify chronological gaps in the representation of women, our study grouped papers by time periods largely based on the paper's content and time frames allocated by module specifications. These periods were: Medieval (c. 400–1485), Early Modern (1485–1750), Modern (1750–present), and Cross-Period.⁷ Most were modern papers (119), followed by early modern papers (55), then medieval papers (31) (Figure 1). Cross-period papers were the smallest group with only 14 papers. The cross-period papers represent broad chronological modules offered only at GCSE (KS4). OCR issued no medieval papers in their GCSE 'A' course or at AS-Level.

Figure 1: Number of papers issued per exam board grouped by exam level and period.⁸

Our interrogation of the source base focused on three areas of exam content: exam essay questions, source extracts (both primary sources and 'interpretations' by historians), as well as mark schemes.⁹ We aimed to quantify the number of women and men referred to in exam content, to examine the frequency with which particular individuals were

⁷ Criteria for organising papers into period groups discussed in Appendix A.

⁸ Appendix B, Table 1.

⁹ In this study 'primary sources' are defined as texts, objects or images produced roughly contemporaneously to the time period being examined to aid with historical analysis, while 'interpretations' are extracts taken from secondary sources by historians to invite discussion of relevant historical debates.

referred to, and count the number of male and female historians quoted in the exam papers.

Total representation of women in exam papers

Our initial investigation showed that in 76 out of the 219 papers, no women were mentioned in any of the exam questions and source extracts, nor were they specified in the mark scheme. Effectively, 34.7% of papers in the June 2023 series had no women in them at all. By comparison there was only one out of 219 exam papers which did not mention named men or groups of men, and this was a relatively short paper of four questions.¹⁰ In order to represent this picture equitably across exam boards, we calculated percentages for the questions compared to the total number of possible questions per exam level and exam board. We found that GCSE papers were the most likely to not include any women (39%), followed by A-Level (33.6%), then AS (31.9%) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Percentage of papers per exam level and exam board where women were not referred to in questions, source extracts or the paper's mark scheme.¹¹

¹⁰ 'Y224/01 Apartheid and Reconciliation: South African Politics 1948–1999', OCR (10 June 2023): <https://www.ocr.org.uk/Images/703681-question-paper-apartheid-and-reconciliation-south-african-politics-1948-1999.pdf>, accessed 14 July 2025.

¹¹ Appendix B, Table 3b.

Total representation of women in exam papers by chronological 'period'

When broken down by medieval, early modern, modern and cross-period groups, our study shows a pronounced difference in the representation of women across time periods. Medieval papers were the most likely not to feature any women at all (41.9%), followed by modern papers (37.8%), then early modern papers (27.3%). Cross-period GCSE papers performed only slightly better with only 21.4% excluding women (Figure 3).

Figure 3: The percentage of papers by time period where women were not referred to at all in questions, source extracts or the paper's mark scheme.¹²

Representation of women in exam questions

The 219 papers contained 991 questions in total. This section first considers the number of questions where students were expected to discuss women or men in their answers. This includes both the content of the exam question and any additional source extracts provided with the question which made reference to women.

Questions on women and men

Students were directed to discuss women (as individuals or groups) in only 59 out of the total 991 questions (6%). Measured by the same standards, students were directed to

¹² Appendix B, Table 3b.

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discuss men (as individuals or groups) in their answers for 362 questions (36.5%).¹³ Students were directed towards answering their questions on women and men through a variety of approaches. In some cases the question focused on a named person or gender-specific group, in others, students were expected to discuss authorship and provenance of source extracts authored by a male or female individual, or to discuss images which depicted individuals or mixed-sex groups.¹⁴

Figure 4: Percentage of possible questions (per exam level) where students were directed to discuss women or men in their answers.¹⁵

Questions on women compared by exam level (KS4/GCSE vs. KS5/AS or A-Level)

When further breaking down these figures by exam level, the disparity in questions on women and men proved to be more pronounced in AS and A Level papers than in GCSE papers (Figure 4). At GCSE, students were directed to discuss women in their answers for 5.9% of questions compared to 22.5% questions on men. Students were directed to discuss women in their answers in 6% of questions at AS compared to 46.3% of questions on men. At A Level, students were again directed to discuss women for 6% of

¹³ Appendix B, Table 4a.

¹⁴ See also Appendix A for the criteria behind this question.

¹⁵ Appendix B, Table 4b.

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questions in comparison to 39.8% of questions on men. Students were directed to discuss women on average in 6% of questions offered overall across all three exam levels. The comparative provision of questions of men, however, varied by exam level with nearly half of the questions offered in AS papers being specific to men or groups of men.

Questions on women compared by time period

This disparity varied considerably across time period groups. In medieval papers, students were directed to discuss women in 1.5% of questions, whereas they were expected to discuss men in 51.9% of questions. For early modern papers, students were directed to discuss women for 9.9% of questions compared to 45.3% of questions on men, and in modern papers students were directed to discuss women for 6% of questions, but men in 32.2% of questions. For cross-period papers, students were directed to discuss women in their answers for 1.4% of possible questions and men for 15.5% of questions (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Percentage of possible questions where students were directed to discuss either women or men across time period groups.¹⁶

¹⁶ Appendix B, Table 4b.

Questions on groups of women

Out of the 991 questions in total, 11 questions focused on women as a gender-specific group. 10 out of these 11 questions were from AS or A-Level papers. There was only 1 question on women as a group for GCSE students.¹⁷ 9 of the 11 questions were on twentieth-century history and focused on women's suffrage, employment, and reproductive rights. 1 question was on the nineteenth-century Ladies' National Association for the Repeal of the Contagious Diseases Acts.¹⁸ Only 1 question was pre-modern and concerned the influence of the wives of Ottoman sultans.¹⁹

Instances of women identified in exam questions

The next stage of the investigation was to count the number of instances women or men were identified in exam questions (not including source extracts, this was counted separately). Across all 991 questions there were 357 instances of individuals being identified in questions (by name, title or moniker). 31 instances were women and the remaining 326 were men (Figure 6). For every 1 instance of a named woman, there were on average 10.5 instances of men.

Instances of women identified in exam questions by exam level

At A-Level women were slightly more visible (9.9 instances of men on average for every 1 instance of an identified woman) and worst represented at AS (11.9 instances of men on average for every 1 instance of a woman). At GCSE the ratio was 10.8 instances of men for every 1 instance of a woman (Figure 7).

¹⁷ Question 6a and 6b in the 'Britain in Peace and War 1900–1918' component of 'J411/13 The People's Health, c.1250 to present with Britain in Peace and War, 1900-1918', OCR (GCSE B) (7 June 2023), <https://www.ocr.org.uk/Images/704821-question-paper-the-people-s-health-c.1250-to-present-with-britain-in-peace-and-war-1900-1918.pdf>, accessed 14 July 2025.

¹⁸ '9HI0/36 Option 36.1: Protest, agitation and parliamentary reform in Britain, c1780–1928', Pearson Edexcel (13 June 2023), <https://qualifications.pearson.com/content/dam/pdf/A-Level/History/2015/Exam-materials/9hi0-36-que-20230614.pdf>, accessed 14 July 2025.

¹⁹ 'Y309/01 The Ascendancy of the Ottoman Empire 1453–1606', OCR (24 May 2023), <https://www.ocr.org.uk/Images/703688-question-paper-the-ascendancy-of-the-ottoman-empire-1453-1606.pdf>, accessed 14 July 2025.

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Figure 6: Comparison of the total number of instances of women and men identified in exam questions across the 2023 series²⁰

Figure 7: Number of instances of women and men identified in exam questions per exam level and exam board.²¹

²⁰ Appendix B, Table 5.

²¹ Appendix B, Table 5.

Instances of women identified in exam questions by time period

The ratio varied more obviously across time period groups. The ratio of identified men for every one identified woman in exam questions was highest in medieval papers (40.5 men for every 1 woman), followed by modern papers (19.3 men for every 1 woman) and cross-period papers (7 men for every 1 woman). Instances of women occurred more often in comparison with men in papers on the early modern period with 4.9 men for every 1 woman (Figure 8), but this appears to be due to the high number of questions on Elizabeth I. Out of the 22 instances of women identified in early modern exam questions, 8 of these instances were of Elizabeth I.

Figure 8: Comparison of number of instances of women and men identified in exam questions across time period groups.²²

Instances of women in source extracts

264 questions out of the total 991 included source extracts for students to discuss. These extracts were typically either primary sources (usually referred to in the question

²² Appendix B, Table 5.

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as a ‘source’) or secondary sources (commonly referred to as ‘interpretations’).²³ This stage of the investigation involved counting the number of instances of women in source extracts. Overall, there were 633 instances of named men in source extracts compared to only 56 instances of named women, meaning that for every 1 instance of a woman in a source, there were 11.3 instances of men.

Instances of women identified in exam questions by exam level

Women were more visible in the sources at GCSE (8.6 instances of men to every 1 instance of a woman) and least visible at AS (17.7 instances of men for every 1 instance of a woman). The ratio for A-Level was 10.3 instances of men on average for every 1 instance of a woman (Figure 9). Compared with the number of instances of women and men identified in exam questions, women were less likely to be identified in AS questions and source extracts than at GCSE or A Level.

Figure 9: Number of instances of women and men identified in source extracts per exam level and exam board.²⁴

²³ See footnote 9 above.

²⁴ Appendix B, Table 6.

Instances of women identified in exam questions by time period

Like exam essay questions, the ratio of instances of women compared to men in source extracts varied sharply across the time period groups. Medieval papers were clearly the least representative. 27 men appeared for every 1 instance of a named woman. Cross-period papers came next (10 men for every 1 woman), modern papers (9.8 men for every 1 woman), and early modern papers (9.7 men for every 1 woman) (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Comparison of number of instances of women and men identified in source extracts across time period groups.²⁵

Source extracts authored by women

Having counted the number of instances of women and men in exam questions and source extracts, the next stage of the investigation involved counting how many of the source extracts, whether as primary sources or interpretations, were authored by identified women.²⁶

²⁵ Appendix B, Table 6.

²⁶ See footnote 9 for distinction between primary sources and interpretations.

Primary source extracts authored by women

When it comes to the authors of primary sources, 217 primary source extracts had an author with a gender that could be inferred either by name or by contextual information such as pronouns in the text.²⁷ Out of the total 217, only 16 were authored by women: 201 were authored by men.

Primary source extracts authored by women by exam level

At GCSE, 6 out of 35 primary source extracts were authored by women. Women wrote 2 out of 60 primary source extracts in AS papers, and 8 out of 122 primary source extracts included in A-Level exams (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Number of primary source extracts authored by women and men across exam levels and exam boards.²⁸

²⁷ Author is defined in this instance as the person who produced the source extract originally, whether they wrote it, created an image or spoke it in speech or interview.

²⁸ Appendix B, Table 7.

Primary source extracts authored by women by time period

Most of the primary source extracts authored by women came from the modern period (Figure 12). None of the 31 primary source extracts in medieval papers were written by women despite there being a very substantial source base of potential materials currently available in translation from letters, poems and songs to religious and secular texts. Early modern papers were almost as bad: out of 49 source extracts only 1 was authored by a woman. By comparison, modern papers showed some improvement as 14 out of 133 were authored by women, the voices of women, who represent 50% of the population, are still chronically underrepresented. The solo primary source extract authored by a woman in a cross-period GCSE paper was modern and attributed to Gwynedd Lloyd, a nurse in World War I.²⁹

Figure 12: Number of primary source extracts authored by women and men by time period.³⁰

Interpretations authored by women historians

In the June 2023 exam papers and mark schemes, 163 historians were quoted in exam papers, and only 22 were women. On average, for every one female historian quoted, 6.4

²⁹ 'Sources Booklet: Medicine in Britain, c1250–present and The British sector of the Western Front, 1914–18: injuries, treatment and the trenches', Pearson Edexcel GCSE, 1HI0/11 (18 May 2023), <https://qualifications.pearson.com/content/dam/pdf/GCSE/History/2016/Exam-materials/1hi0-11-que-20230519.pdf>, accessed 14 July 2025.

³⁰ Appendix B, Table 7.

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male historians were platformed. 88 historians were presented in ‘gender neutral’ terms often with only an initial and surname (e.g. A. Smith), which can be positive but also masks the problem rather than encouraging equality. 75 historians were presented in the exam papers with their full name making their gender more visible, but only 8 were women in comparison to 67 men. If women are to be visible in the curriculum, the names and voices of female academic historians need to be present alongside actual examples of historical women.

Figure 13: Number of historians (women and men) quoted in exam papers across exam boards and exam levels.³¹

Interpretations authored by women historians by exam level

The gender disparity between female and male historians varied between exam levels (Figure 13). AS papers were the least inclusive, with 11.7 men to 1 woman. GCSE papers fared better (4.2 men to every 1 woman) and A Level papers had a ratio of 6.2 men to every 1 woman. OCR’s GCSE ‘A’ and AS papers made no reference to female historians.

³¹ Appendix B, Table 8.

Interpretations authored by women historians by time period

Time period groups also revealed distinct patterns (Figure 14). Medieval papers were least likely to include female historians (21 men to 1 woman), followed by modern papers (8.6 men to 1 woman). The early modern period cited more female historians, but men still outnumbered women by 3.1 to 1. There were no quoted historians in any cross-period papers.

Figure 14: Number of historians (women and men) quoted in exam papers across time periods.³²

³² Appendix B, Table 9.

Representation of women in mark schemes

The following section included counting the number of questions where women and men were referenced in the mark schemes. It may be argued that where questions do not specifically mention women, it is still possible for students to reference women's experiences in their responses to questions. However, successful assessments are achieved by students adhering to the content in the mark schemes. If women do not appear in the indicative content, discussing them in an exam answer might not only be seen as irrelevant to the desired response, it might be marked as a wrong answer. Therefore to ensure inclusivity in History assessments, it is crucial to ensure that references to women are an essential element of a successful exam answer.

Questions with references to women in the mark scheme

In the June 2023 exam mark schemes, women appeared as possible indicative content (either as named individuals or gender-specific groups) for 226 out of 991 questions (22.8%). Based on the same criteria, men appeared in the mark scheme for 824 questions (83.1%). On average, for every 1 question that included women as indicative content in the mark scheme, there were 3.6 questions that included men (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Comparison of percentages of questions where women or men were included as indicative content in the mark schemes.³³

³³ Appendix B, Table 8.

Questions with references to women in the mark scheme by exam level

The ratio of number of questions where women were included as indicative content compared to men was largely consistent across all the exam levels. GCSE had the lowest ratio (3.5 questions with men for every 1 question with women), while AS had the highest ratio (3.8 questions with men for every 1 question with women). The ratio for A Level was 3.6 questions with men for every 1 question with women in the mark scheme (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Number of questions with examples of women and men (as individuals or gender-specific groups) as indicative content in the mark scheme across exam levels and exam boards.³⁴

Questions with references to women in the mark scheme by time period

The ratios for mark schemes were more varied across the time period groups. Modern papers were the least inclusive with 4.5 questions with men included as indicative content in the mark scheme for every 1 question with women, followed closely by medieval papers (4.3 questions with men in the mark scheme for every 1 question with women). Early modern papers specified more women in the mark schemes (2.4

³⁴ Appendix B, Table 8.

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questions with men for every 1 question with women) while cross-period papers had a ratio of 3.5 questions with men for every 1 question with women (Figure 17). The prevalence of early modern women can again be attributed to the 'Elizabeth I effect'. Out of 81 early modern questions with references to women in the mark scheme, Elizabeth I appeared in the mark scheme for 35 of these questions.

Figure 17: Number of questions with examples of women and men (as individuals or gender-specific groups) as indicative content in the mark scheme across time periods.³⁵

The figures expressed above do not quantify how many of instances women and men were provided in the mark schemes for each question, only whether at least one reference was made. When the number of examples is counted, the disparity becomes much worse. Across all the mark schemes for all the exam papers, there were 2539 references to men, and 352 references to women, an average of 7.2 references to men for every 1 reference concerning women.

³⁵ Appendix B, Table 8.

Women identified in exam papers

Across all exam questions, source extracts and mark schemes, 128 individual women were named. While at first glance this may seem a credible number, 79 of these individual women only appear in the mark scheme and not in the exam content (questions and source extracts) where students can see them. At GCSE, of 35 named women only 11 appeared in exam questions and source extracts. At AS there were 30 individual women of which 9 appeared in exam questions and source extracts. A-Level had the largest number of individual women at 91, but only 35 appeared in exam questions and source extracts.

The appearance of some individuals was clearly disproportionate. The most frequently referenced women were Elizabeth I (55 references), followed by Mary I (21 references) and Margaret Thatcher (15 references) (Figure 18). Elizabeth I was the only woman referred to in exam questions, source extracts and mark schemes across all exam levels and from each of the three exam boards.

Figure 18: The most frequently referenced women in exam questions, source extracts and mark schemes combined.³⁶

³⁶ Appendix C.

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Of the top 11 women most frequently referred to, 9 were royal women of which 6 women were queens regnant or consort of England. The other two women were Margaret Thatcher, the first female Prime Minister, and the suffragette Emmeline Pankhurst.

In our study of the June 2023 exam papers, modern women were the best represented in terms of individuals (61 women), followed by early modern women (45). Medieval women were the smallest group with only 22 individuals included. Only 2 medieval women were named in actual questions: Margaret of Anjou and Elizabeth Woodville, who were both fifteenth-century English queen-consorts, chronologically right at the end of the Middle Ages. Medieval women did not appear in any questions or source extracts in GCSE papers (Figure 19) and were thus primarily confined to medieval History AS and A Level exam papers.

Figure 19: Number of individual women referenced in student-facing exam content (exam questions and source extracts, excluding mark schemes) at each exam level and by time period.³⁷

³⁷ Appendix C.

Overall findings

Across all History exam materials and at all assessment levels, the June 2023 assessments produced by the three main exam boards in England critically underrepresented women, as historic individuals, as groups and as academic historians. Despite women constituting approximately half of past and present populations, no women appeared in the questions, source extracts or mark schemes for 34.7% of the papers offered. Students were directed to discuss women in their answers for only 6% of questions on average compared to 37% of questions on men. Out of 351 instances of individuals named in questions, only 31 were women and out of 689 instances of individuals named in source extracts only 56 were women. The gaps in representation can vary by exam level and time period, but not in one paper or mark scheme were they present in numbers that could be called anywhere close to representative of modern society.

The divide between the representation of women and men in exam content was narrower at GCSE, compared to AS and A Level, but this was generally because questions at GCSE typically did not focus on individual women or men. Representation of women at GCSE was notably limited. Only 2 named women appeared in GCSE questions in June 2023, Elizabeth I and Mary Queen of Scots. Women were more likely to appear in A-Level content than at GCSE and AS-Level, but men also appeared more frequently in A-Level content and combined with a higher proportion of questions and source extracts focused on men, this gap in representation is actually wider.

Different time periods also exposed considerable disparity in equal representation. Modern papers, as the largest group, tended to also have the highest number of women featured in exam content, but when considering the exam papers proportionately, women were better represented in early modern papers in comparison to men, though they were still not equally represented. Women were barely visible at all in medieval papers with students directed to discuss women in 2% of questions compared to 52% of questions on men. For every one woman named in an exam question in a medieval paper, there were on average 41 named men in questions, and for every one instance of a woman appearing in a source extract there were 27 instances of men. This is completely inconsistent with actual historical experience, underpinned by

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decades of substantial of academic and public scholarship, evidenced by countless surviving female-authored source materials and artefacts; many of which are freely available online; many of which detail diverse life experiences; and many of which could be easily accessed and incorporated by the schools and exam boards who select the topics they teach to children. It is, simply, 'bad' History. This, in turn, is bad for society.

Exam boards seemed to offer slight improvements in one area compared to others. OCR tended to have the lowest ratio of questions where students were directed to discuss men compared to questions on women. Edexcel had the lowest ratio of named men to named women in source extracts. AQA had the lowest ratio of quoted male historians to women historians. There is still an urgent need for improvement in representation of women across all three exam boards and in the GCSE, AS and A Level papers they issue.

An area of particular concern is the underrepresentation of female historians as the limited representation of women historians. That male historians quoted in exam papers outnumbered female historians by 6.4 to 1 does not correspond with the current academic field where 46.9% of UK academic staff working in History in the 2023–24 academic year were female.³⁸ Nor does it correspond with the composition of students studying History in the UK. Every year since 2019, the number of new female students in History at GCSE, A Level and university have outnumbered male students in the subject.³⁹ Despite the evident popularity of the subject for female students, the current state of the field is not translating into exam assessments where women historians remain a minority. This gap in representing women historians was most pronounced in medieval papers with only one woman historian out of 22 historians.

Another issue is the way particular examples of 'exceptional' women are overrepresented at the expense of others. An example of this is counted in the report as the 'Elizabeth I Effect' to indicate where the frequent appearances of one woman skew the data for the entire group. Elizabeth I was clearly a popular subject in UK History lessons and she is named in GCSE, AS and A Level papers issued by all three exam

³⁸ HESA, 'HE Staff Data: What areas do they work in?' (18 January 2025), <https://www.hesa.ac.uk/data-and-analysis/staff/areas>, accessed 14 July 2025.

³⁹ Royal Historical Society, 'Data on the UK Historical Profession and Discipline' (5 November 2023, updated in 2024 and 2025), <https://blog.royalhistsoc.org/2023/11/05/data-for-the-historical-profession/>, accessed 14 July 2025.

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boards, appearing in 9 questions and 8 source extracts overall. The frequency in which she appeared, however, may explain why early modern papers performed comparatively better in representation of women than other periods. When considering the top eleven most frequently referenced women in the exam papers, Elizabeth I stands at the top of a list of elite women, 9 of whom were royal. The only exceptions on this list were Emmeline Pankhurst and Margaret Thatcher indicating where examples of non-elite women's involvement in politics are limited to the twentieth century.

Based on the 2023 data, two concentrated topics emerge where women tend to feature more frequently in assessments. Papers on the early modern period appear to offer more opportunities to explore women compared to other periods, but these are strongly focused on royal Tudor women. The other broad topic was the twentieth century: 9 out of 11 questions on women as a social group were focused on this period. These questions primarily concerned suffrage, the Home Front, and women's rights. For the rest of the assessment topics, there is little to no representation, leaving historical women unseen and unheard. In the 2023 GCSE, AS and A-Level papers, no women appeared before the fifteenth century and, aside from a few elite Tudors, seemingly sat idle until the Suffrage movement. And, although the focus of this study has been on exam content at Key Stages 4 and 5, what appears in these exams impacts on what history is taught lower down at school, in Key Stage 3 (ages 11-14), the last period in which History at school is still largely compulsory. By concentrating on token, 'exceptional' figures like Elizabeth I and presenting women's political activism as a purely twentieth-century phenomenon, schools and exam boards reinforce and inculcate inaccurate history that overlooks the achievements and contributions that women have made to human existence, especially before the sixteenth century and beyond Britain.

Recommendations

We are conscious of the enormous challenges facing teachers at present, as well as the pressures on school time and resources. We are also aware of the 'evolution not revolution' approach recommended by the curriculum review.⁴⁰ Therefore the

⁴⁰ DfE, 'Curriculum and Assessment Review Interim Report' (March 2025), p. 28, https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/6821d69eced319d02c9060e3/Curriculum_and_Assessment_Review_interim_report.pdf, accessed 14 July 2025.

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recommendations we have for assessments are largely focussed on Ofqual and the exam boards who set the standards for evaluating subject-level achievement in schools. Ofqual states that achieving a qualification in history should enable students to 'extend their knowledge and understanding of ... the wide diversity of human experience' and yet currently c. 50% of the global population are entirely missing from some assessment papers, and poorly represented in others.⁴¹ The current provision for assessment in History for both GCSE and A-Level does not meet the standards required for inclusivity, and is marginalising women's roles in society in a way that reinforces misogynistic narratives. We are making recommendations which do not necessarily require the delivery of time and resource-intensive new modules, but rather a deliberate change in attitude and focus, supported by existing research and scholarship, which could also be delivered in collaboration with HE and teacher training providers. Changing assessments is critical to securing change and will empower teachers to insert women into their History teaching in a meaningful way. It will allow students to see their own pasts and empathise with different experiences, and ultimately promote the values of equality, diversity and inclusion that help a society to flourish.

In light of our investigation into the June 2023 History assessments in England, the Teaching Medieval Women group recommend the following courses of action:

- Every paper for every module should offer opportunities to discuss women in history and this should be highlighted as a recognised response in the mark scheme. Where possible, there should be as many named women as men.
- Increase the representation of a diverse range of women in assessment questions and mark schemes to ensure that diverse women's experiences are represented at GCSE and A-Level.
- Increase the number of pre-modern women in module specifications and course materials, including female-authored primary source extracts or material objects associated with women.

⁴¹ DfE, 'History GCSE subject content', in Ofqual, 'GCSE Subject Level Conditions and Requirements for History' (February 2015), p. 13, <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a74dfa9ed915d502d6cbae0/gcse-subject-level-conditions-and-requirements-for-history.pdf>, accessed 21 July 2025.

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- Provide materials, both online and in textbooks at appropriate levels to support this change.
- Provide questions which allow students more opportunities to discuss women in their answers and include reflections which consider women's experiences as a valued part of the mark scheme.
- Use more gender-neutral language in assessments to provide options for including women, for example swapping 'king' for 'ruler', in medieval contexts.
- Deliver an equal balance of quoted material or 'interpretations' from male and female historians in course materials and assessments.
- Set up an effective, national programme of CPD drawing from academic, teacher and teacher educator expertise which offers a freely available suite of resources to support change. These resources should highlight women from different social and cultural backgrounds, across all time periods. They should reflect the topics represented in the national curriculum and the modules offered by exam boards. The resources should be high quality, stage-appropriate and pedagogically engaging materials on women that are easily accessible online and dovetail with the new assessment requirements to include women.

Appendices

Appendix A – Explaining the criteria

Determining time periods of papers

This survey grouped papers into time period groups based on the paper's content.

These periods were: Medieval (c. 400–1485), Early Modern (1485–1750), Modern (1750–Present), and Cross-Period (breadth topics at GCSE only which cover topics from the medieval period to the modern).

Where papers crossed period divides, for example a paper on England 1450–1509 was designated a medieval paper as the majority of the time span covered in the paper corresponded with the medieval period group.

Questions where students were directed to discuss women or men (as named individuals or groups) in their answer

There were varying ways in which students were directed to discuss women or men in their answers. Common ways of directing students included:

- Focusing the question on a named person, such as their character, their government, their policies, etc.
- Focusing the question on a gender-specific group (e.g. kings, earls) or a group that would be gender-specific based on the time period (e.g. twentieth-century US presidents).
- Students being prompted to discuss a named person or gender-specific group in answer.
- Students being expected to discuss the provenance and authorship of a source with an identified (by name or gender) author.
- The use of image sources depicting named or gendered individual/s where students were expected to discuss the source contents.

Questions that used individuals as a means of distinguishing time periods, e.g. Edwardian, Elizabethan, the reign of Elizabeth I, were not counted. Likewise, wider movements associated with a person, such as Stalinism, were not counted.

Counting instances compared to individuals

Named individuals were identified either as named persons (e.g. Edward I), through a moniker (William Rufus), or titled persons who could be identified as a historical question (e.g. the earl of Warwick in a question relating to 1460s politics).

Instances were references to individuals. For example, Elizabeth I was one individual but appeared in 55 instances.

Instances were counted only once per question or source extract, even if they appeared multiple times in the same question or source extract.

References in the mark scheme

Mark schemes often offered indicative content and sample answers to questions.

References are defined as instances when a gendered individual or group were referred to in the mark scheme. These instances were only counted once per question.

Appendix B – Data tables**Table 1: Number of exam papers divided by exam level, exam board and period**

Exam board	Exam level	Medieval	Early Modern	Modern	Cross-period	Total
AQA	GCSE	2	2	9	3	16
	AS	3	4	16	0	23
	A Level	3	8	19	0	30
Edexcel	GCSE	2	4	7	4	17
	AS	2	3	11	0	16
	A Level	3	6	17	0	26
OCR	GCSE A	0	3	7	4	14
	GCSE B	3	3	3	3	12
	AS	0	3	5	0	8
	A Level	13	19	25	0	57
TOTAL		31	55	119	14	219

Table 2: Total number of exam questions per exam level, exam board and period

Exam board	Exam level	Medieval	Early Modern	Modern	Cross-period	Total
AQA	GCSE	8	8	44	12	72
	AS	9	12	48		69
	A Level	12	32	76		120
Edexcel	GCSE	8	14	33	24	79
	AS	15	20	86		121
	A Level	16	31	120		167
OCR	GCSE A		6	31	14	51
	GCSE B	16	16	16	21	69
	AS		12	16		28
	A Level	47	72	96		215
TOTAL		131	223	566	71	991

Table 3a: Number of exam papers where women were not referred to in either the exam question, source extracts or the mark scheme compared to the total number of questions per exam level, exam board and period

Exam board	Exam level	Medieval	Early Modern	Modern	Cross-period	Total
AQA	GCSE	2	0	4	1	7
	AS	0	1	8		9
	A Level	0	1	8		9
Edexcel	GCSE	2	1	5		8
	AS	1	0	4		5
	A Level	1	2	2		5
OCR	GCSE A		2	1	2	5
	GCSE B	1	1	1	0	3
	AS		1	0		1
	A Level	6	6	12		24
Total		13	15	45	3	76

Table 3b: Percentages of exam papers where women were not referred to in either the exam question, source extracts or the mark scheme compared to the total number of questions per exam level, exam board and period

Exam board	Exam level	Medieval	Early Modern	Modern	Cross-period	Average total
AQA	GCSE	100	0	44.4	33.3	43.8
	AS	0	25	50		39.1
	A Level	0	12.5	42.1		30
Edexcel	GCSE	100	25	71.4	0	47.1
	AS	50	0	36.4		31.3
	A Level	33.3	33.3	11.8		19.2
OCR	GCSE A		66.7	14.3	50	35.7
	GCSE B	33.3	33.3	33.3	0	25
	AS		33.3	0		12.5
	A Level	46.2	31.6	48.0		42.1
Total		41.9	27.3	37.8	21.4	34.7

Table 4a: Number of exam questions where students were directed to discuss women and men in their answer per exam level, exam board and period

Exam board	Exam level	Medieval		Early Modern		Modern		Cross-period		Total	
		Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men
AQA	GCSE	0	2	1	1	4	11	0	3	5	17
	AS	1	4	1	9	1	20			3	33
	A Level	1	8	3	17	4	34			8	59
Edexcel	GCSE	0	5	1	4	1	8	1	6	3	23
	AS	0	10	2	10	6	34			8	54
	A Level	0	9	1	18	9	35			10	62
OCR	GCSE A			0	3	4	8	0	2	4	13
	GCSE B	0	3	2	4	2	1	0	0	4	8
	AS			1	8	1	6			2	14
	A Level	0	27	10	27	2	25			12	79
TOTAL		2	68	22	101	34	182	1	11	59	362

Table 4b: Percentages of exam questions where students were directed to discuss women and men in their answer compared to the total number of questions per exam level, exam board and period

Exam board	Exam level	Medieval		Early Modern		Modern		Cross-period		Total	
		Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men
AQA	GCSE	0	25	12.5	12.5	9.1	25	0	25	6.9	23.6
	AS	11.1	44.4	8.3	75	2.1	41.7			4.3	47.8
	A Level	8.3	66.7	9.4	53.1	5.3	44.7			6.7	49.2
Edexcel	GCSE	0	62.5	7.1	28.6	3	24.2	4.2	25	3.8	29.1
	AS	0	66.7	10	50	7	39.5			6.6	44.6
	A Level	0	56.3	3.2	58.1	7.5	29.2			6.0	37.1
OCR	GCSE A			0	50	12.9	25.8	0	14.3	7.8	25.5
	GCSE B	0	18.8	12.5	25	12.5	6.3	0	0	5.8	11.6
	AS			8.3	66.7	6.3	37.5			7.1	50.0
	A Level	0	57.4	13.9	37.5	2.1	26			5.6	36.7
TOTAL		1.5	51.9	9.9	45.3	6.0	32.2	1.4	15.5	6.0	36.5

Table 5: Number of instances of women and men identified in exam questions per exam level, exam board and period

Exam board	Exam level	Medieval		Early Modern		Modern		Cross-period		Total		
		Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Combined
AQA	GCSE	0	4	1	2	0	7	0	3	1	16	17
	AS	1	5	1	8	0	13			2	26	28
	A Level	1	12	4	15	1	25			6	52	58
Edexcel	GCSE	0	6	1	5	0	7	0	3	1	21	22
	AS	0	13	2	9	1	21			3	43	46
	A Level	0	9	1	19	4	30			5	58	63
OCR	GCSE A			0	5	0	2	1	1	1	8	9
	GCSE B	0	2	2	6	0	1	0	0	2	9	11
	AS			1	8	1	6			2	14	16
	A Level	0	30	8	26	0	23			8	79	87
TOTAL		2	81	21	103	7	135	1	7	31	326	357

Table 6: Number of instances of women and men identified in source extracts per exam level, exam board and period

Exam board	Exam level	Medieval		Early Modern		Modern		Cross-period		Total		
		Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Combined
AQA	GCSE	0	0	0	1	3	17	0	3	3	21	24
	AS	2	25	0	17	1	36			3	78	81
	A Level	0	19	4	27	4	59			8	105	113
Edexcel	GCSE	0	0	0	0	2	18	1	5	3	23	26
	AS	1	15	3	12	3	49			7	76	83
	A Level	0	16	2	26	13	76			15	118	133
OCR	GCSE A			1	12	1	10	0	2	2	24	26
	GCSE B	0	9	1	8	1	1	0	0	2	18	20
	AS			0	20	0	3			0	23	23
	A Level	2	51	9	70	2	26			13	147	160
TOTAL		5	135	20	193	30	295	1	10	56	633	689

Table 7: Number of primary source extracts authored by identified women or men per exam level, exam board and period

Exam board	Exam level	Medieval		Early Modern		Modern		Cross-period		Total		
		Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Combined
AQA	GCSE	0	0	0	0	3	11	0	0	3	11	14
	AS	0	2	0	4	0	16			0	22	22
	A Level	0	5	0	9	3	29			3	43	46
Edexcel	GCSE	0	0	0	0	2	3	1	3	3	6	9
	AS	0	3	0	3	2	18			2	24	26
	A Level	0	4	0	4	4	25			4	33	37
OCR	GCSE A			0	5	0	2	0	0	0	7	7
	GCSE B	0	3	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	5	5
	AS			0	9	0	3			0	12	12
	A Level	0	14	1	13	0	11			1	38	39
TOTAL		5	31	1	48	14	119	1	3	16	201	217

Table 8: Number of questions where women and men are identified as indicative content in mark schemes per exam level, exam board and period

Exam board	Exam level	Medieval		Early Modern		Modern		Cross-period		Total		
		Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Combined
AQA	GCSE	0	8	6	8	8	28	3	11	17	55	72
	AS	3	9	4	12	9	47			16	68	84
	A Level	7	12	12	31	12	70			31	113	144
Edexcel	GCSE	0	7	6	12	3	19	3	13	12	51	63
	AS	4	15	8	18	15	70			27	103	130
	A Level	4	16	11	27	25	103			40	146	186
OCR	GCSE A			2	5	7	26	4	12	13	43	56
	GCSE B	1	13	3	11	6	10	3	9	13	43	56
	AS			3	11	5	14			8	25	33
	A Level	10	44	26	61	13	72			49	177	226
TOTAL		29	124	81	196	103	459	13	45	226	824	1050

Table 9: Number of named historians quoted per exam level, exam board and period

Exam board	Exam level	Medieval		Early Modern		Modern		Cross-period		Total		
		Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Women	Men	Combined
AQA	GCSE	0	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	3	4
	AS	0	2	1	2	1	9			2	13	15
	A Level	0	2	2	6	3	15			5	23	28
Edexcel	GCSE	0	0	0	0	2	10	0	0	2	10	12
	AS	0	2	0	5	1	10			1	17	18
	A Level	0	3	1	3	0	12			1	18	19
OCR	GCSE A			0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1
	GCSE B	0	3	1	4	2	4	0	0	3	11	14
	AS			0	0	0	5			0	5	5
	A Level	1	7	5	13	1	20			7	40	47
TOTAL		1	21	11	34	10	86	0	0	22	141	163

Appendix C – Women identified (by name, moniker or title) in exam content in the 2023 series by exam level

Individual	Period	Number of questions where individual was named in the question				Number of questions where individual was named in source extracts				Number of questions where individual was referred to in the mark scheme				Overall Total
		GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	
Elizabeth I	Early Modern	3	3	3	9	1	2	5	8	12	7	19	38	55
Mary I	Early Modern			2	2	1		4	5	3		11	14	21
Margaret Thatcher	Modern		2	2	4	1	1	2	4	1	3	3	7	15
Catherine of Aragon	Early Modern			1	1				0	1	4	4	9	10
Isabella of Castile	Early Modern			2	2				0	2		5	7	9
Mary Queen of Scots	Early Modern	2			2				0	3		4	7	9
Margaret of Anjou	Medieval		1		1		1		1		2	4	6	8
Tsarina Alexandra	Modern			1	1			1	1	1	1	3	5	7
Elizabeth Woodville	Medieval			1	1							5	5	6
Emmeline Pankhurst	Modern			1	1	1		1	2	1	1	1	3	6
Mary II	Early Modern			1	1			2	2		1	2	3	6
Anne Boleyn	Early Modern		1		1					1	1	1	3	4
Diane Nash	Modern					1			1	3			3	4

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Individual	Period	Number of questions where individual was named in the question				Number of questions where individual was named in source extracts				Number of questions where individual was referred to in the mark scheme				Overall Total
		GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	
Henrietta Maria	Early Modern									1	1	2	4	4
Jiang Qing	Modern										2	2	4	4
Katherine Johnson	Modern					1			1	3			3	4
Eleanor of Aquitaine	Medieval										2	1	3	3
Harriet Beecher Stowe	Modern						1		1	1		1	2	3
Louis XIV's mother (Anne of Austria)	Early Modern							2	2			1	1	3
Marie Antoinette	Modern							1	1		1	1	2	3
Mathilda of Flanders	Medieval						1		1		1	1	2	3
Betty Scholem	Modern							1	1			1	1	2
Bobbie Battista	Modern						1		1		1		1	2
Catherine the Great	Early Modern			1	1							1	1	2
Christabel Pankhurst	Modern							1	1			1	1	2
Eleanor Roosevelt	Modern									1		1	2	2
Emma Goldman	Modern					1			1	1			1	2
Empress Cixi	Modern			1	1							1	1	2
Empress Elizabeth of Russia	Early Modern			1	1							1	1	2
Empress Matilda	Medieval							1	1			1	1	2

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Individual	Period	Number of questions where individual was named in the question				Number of questions where individual was named in source extracts				Number of questions where individual was referred to in the mark scheme				Overall Total
		GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	
Florence Nightingale	Modern									1		1	2	2
Françoise d'Aubigné, Madame de Maintenon	Early Modern			1	1							1	1	2
Gwynedd Lloyd	Modern					1			1	1			1	2
Hsu Kuang	Modern						1		1		1		1	2
Lucy Hutchinson	Early Modern							1	1			1	1	2
Lydia Dan	Modern					1			1	1			1	2
Marianne Schweitzer	Modern							1	1			1	1	2
Melita Maschmann	Modern							1	1			1	1	2
Meridel Le Sueur	Modern							1	1			1	1	2
Miriam Farley	Modern							1	1			1	1	2
Mrs (Emmeline) Pethick-Lawrence	Modern							1	1			1	1	2
Olga Friedenberg	Modern							1	1			1	1	2
Phyllis Schlafly	Modern									1	1		2	2
Queen Anne	Early Modern											2	2	2
Queen Victoria	Modern							1	1			1	1	2
Ray Strachley	Modern							1	1			1	1	2

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Individual	Period	Number of questions where individual was named in the question				Number of questions where individual was named in source extracts				Number of questions where individual was referred to in the mark scheme				Overall Total
		GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	
Regent Sophia	Early Modern			1	1							1	1	2
Sara Maitland	Modern							1	1			1	1	2
Sarah Palin	Modern									1		1	2	2
Sibylla of Jerusalem	Medieval									1		1	2	2
Sophie Scholl	Modern									2			2	2
Sultana Roxelana	Early Modern							1	1			1	1	2
Teresa of Avila	Early Modern											2	2	2
Aethelflaed	Medieval											1	1	1
Agnes (wife of Amalric)	Medieval											1	1	1
Aleksandra Kollontai	Modern										1		1	1
Althea Jones Lecointe	Modern									1			1	1
Anne Askew	Early Modern										1		1	1
Annie Besant	Modern											1	1	1
Aphra Behn	Early Modern									1			1	1
Bess of Hardwick	Early Modern									1			1	1

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Individual	Period	Number of questions where individual was named in the question				Number of questions where individual was named in source extracts				Number of questions where individual was referred to in the mark scheme				Overall Total
		GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	
Bessie Smith	Modern										1		1	1
Betty Friedan	Modern									1			1	1
Brithvea (woman cured after Becket's death)	Medieval										1		1	1
Catherine de Medici	Early Modern											1	1	1
Catherine of Braganza	Early Modern											1	1	1
Catherine Parr	Early Modern											1	1	1
Christabel Bielenberg	Modern											1	1	1
Conan's (count of Brittany) daughter	Medieval										1		1	1
Duchess of Parma (Louise Marie Thérèse d'Artois)	Modern											1	1	1
Elise Hampel	Modern									1			1	1
Elizabeth Barry	Early Modern									1			1	1
Elizabeth II	Modern											1	1	1

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Individual	Period	Number of questions where individual was named in the question				Number of questions where individual was named in source extracts				Number of questions where individual was referred to in the mark scheme				Overall Total
		GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	
Elizabeth of York	Early Modern											1	1	1
Elizabeth Wolstenholme	Modern											1	1	1
Emma of Normandy	Medieval											1	1	1
Empress Anna of Russia	Early Modern											1	1	1
Empress Catherine I of Russia	Early Modern											1	1	1
Frances Perkins	Modern											1	1	1
Gytha of Wessex	Medieval										1		1	1
Hannah Greener	Modern									1			1	1
Hannah More	Modern									1			1	1
Harriet Martineau	Modern											1	1	1
Heike Drechsler	Modern										1		1	1
Henry II's daughter (Matilda, duchess of Saxony)	Medieval											1	1	1
Henry III's sister (Eleanor)	Medieval									1			1	1
Henry IV's mother (Blanche of Lancaster)	Medieval											1	1	1

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Individual	Period	Number of questions where individual was named in the question				Number of questions where individual was named in source extracts				Number of questions where individual was referred to in the mark scheme				Overall Total
		GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	
Hillary Clinton	Modern											1	1	1
Infanta Isabella of Spain	Early Modern							1	1					1
Infanta Maria Anna of Spain	Early Modern											1	1	1
Isabelle of Valois (Richard II's wife)	Medieval							1	1					1
James I's daughter (Elizabeth)	Early Modern											1	1	1
James I's wife (Anne of Denmark)	Early Modern										1		1	1
Jane Wenham	Early Modern											1	1	1
Joan of Arc	Medieval											1	1	1
Joanna of Castile	Early Modern											1	1	1
Josephine Butler	Modern											1	1	1
Katarina Witt	Modern										1		1	1
Lady Jane Grey	Early Modern											1	1	1
Liselotte, Madame Palatine	Early Modern											1	1	1

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Individual	Period	Number of questions where individual was named in the question				Number of questions where individual was named in source extracts				Number of questions where individual was referred to in the mark scheme				Overall Total
		GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	
Louise de Krouaille	Early Modern											1	1	1
Margaret Beaufort	Medieval											1	1	1
Margaret Clitherow	Early Modern									1			1	1
Margaret of Burgundy	Medieval											1	1	1
Margaret of Parma	Early Modern										1		1	1
Margaret Tudor	Early Modern											1	1	1
Maria of Austria	Early Modern											1	1	1
Marianne Grtner	Modern					1			1					1
Marie de Medici	Early Modern											1	1	1
Marie Stopes	Modern											1	1	1
Marie Theresa	Early Modern											1	1	1
Marlene Dietrich	Modern									1			1	1
Mary Macarthur	Modern											1	1	1
Mary McLeod Bethune	Modern										1		1	1

Finding Women in School Assessments: Appendices

Individual	Period	Number of questions where individual was named in the question				Number of questions where individual was named in source extracts				Number of questions where individual was referred to in the mark scheme				Overall Total
		GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	
Mary Tudor (sister of Henry VIII)	Early Modern											1	1	1
Mary Whitehouse	Modern										1		1	1
Melisende of Jerusalem	Medieval											1	1	1
Muriel, Countess de la Warr	Modern							1	1					1
Nancy Astor	Modern											1	1	1
Nell Gwynn	Early Modern									1			1	1
Neville Chamberlain's unnamed sister	Modern							1	1					1
Pope Paul III's mistress	Early Modern											1	1	1
Princess Diana	Modern									1			1	1
Queen of Prussia (Augusta of Saxe-Weimar)	Modern							1	1					1
Rosa Parks	Modern									1			1	1
Sister of James III of Scotland (Margaret Stewart)	Medieval						1		1					1

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Individual	Period	Number of questions where individual was named in the question				Number of questions where individual was named in source extracts				Number of questions where individual was referred to in the mark scheme				Overall Total
		GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	GCSE	AS	A Level	Total	
Unnamed 7th century Kentish princess married to Edwin of Northumbria	Medieval											1	1	1
Ursula Bright	Modern											1	1	1
TOTAL		5	7	19	31	10	9	37	56	57	42	140	239	326